

A Comparative Study on Impact of Non Performing Assests (NPA) on Profitability of SBI and HDFC

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Research Paper

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ABSTRACT

This research explores the impact of Non-Performing Assets (NPA) on the profitability of HDFC Bank and State Bank of India (SBI). NPAs can negatively affect banks' financial performance by increasing provisioning needs and reducing income. Using a quantitative approach, this study analyzes financial statements and NPA metrics from both banks over a set period. It aims to quantify the relationship between NPA levels and profitability indicators like Return on Assets (ROA) and Return on Equity (ROE). By comparing HDFC Bank's strong asset quality with SBI's larger and more diverse portfolio, the research provides insights into how different asset management and risk strategies impact profitability and offers recommendations for enhancing asset quality and financial stability.

INTRODUCTION

Non-Performing Assets (NPA) represent a critical challenge for banks, reflecting loans or advances that are overdue and have not been repaid for a specified period. NPAs are a key indicator of asset quality and financial health, impacting a bank's profitability and stability. High levels of NPAs increase the need for loan loss provisions, thereby reducing net income and affecting overall financial performance. This problem is particularly pronounced in the banking sector, where effective management of NPAs is crucial for maintaining financial stability and operational efficiency. Understanding the dynamics of

NPAs, including their effect on profitability and risk management practices, is essential for assessing the health of banks and developing strategies to mitigate financial risks.

OBJECTIVE OF STUDY

Following is the Objective of the Study

1. To Study the Impact of NPA on Profitability of selected bank

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The Statement of the Problem defines the specific issue or gap in knowledge that a research study aims to address. It outlines the context and significance of the problem, highlighting the need for investigation and the potential impact of finding a solution. This framework guides the research focus and objectives.

1. Is the Non-Performing Asset affecting the profitability of selected banks ?

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

1. **Anilkumar Ramashare Nirmal & Dr. Purvi Derashri (2020)** highlight the performance disparity between HDFC Bank and SBI, noting HDFC's superior profitability and lower Gross NPAs compared to SBI, despite the latter's strong public sector presence. Their study underscores the performance gap between private and public sector banks in India.
2. **C Esakkiammal et al. (2020)** examine NPA management at HDFC Bank and SBI, noting HDFC's stronger financial performance and lower NPAs compared to SBI, which, while outperforming other public sector banks, lags behind private sector counterparts. The study emphasizes differences in NPA management between the two sectors.
3. **Reetika Verma (2021)** uses ratio analysis to compare HDFC and SBI's financial performance from 2015 to 2020, finding HDFC superior in profitability and customer satisfaction. The study highlights the performance differences between private and public sector banks but notes limitations due to its reliance on secondary data.
4. **Kishan Chaudhary & Harshad Chaudhary (2013)** compare NPA management in public and private sector banks, revealing higher NPAs in public banks. Their analysis shows a positive

correlation between NPA and various sectors in public banks, with private banks managing NPAs better. The study suggests a need for improved strategies in public sector banks.

5. **K Karthikeyan & M Dinesh Kumar (2023)** analyze SBI and HDFC Bank's financial performance from 2017-22, finding HDFC Bank's superior in branch and ATM expansion. The study highlights both banks' improvements in loan provision and NPA management but notes limitations due to its reliance on secondary data.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research methodology for A Comparative Study On Impact Of Non Performing Assests (NPA) On Profitability of SBI and HDFC Bank over five financial years (2018-19 to 2022-23) using secondary data from annual reports is outlined as follows. The study begins with data collection, where the annual reports of SBI and HDFC Bank for the specified years will be obtained from their official websites or financial databases. This process is expected to take 2 weeks. Relevant NPA data, including Gross NPAs, Net NPAs, and NPA ratios (Gross NPA Ratio, Net NPA Ratio), will be extracted and organized for analysis.

Following data collection, data analysis will be conducted over a period of 4 weeks. This phase involves descriptive analysis to calculate basic statistics like mean, median, and standard deviation of NPAs for both banks. Trend analysis will be performed to plot the changes in Gross and Net NPAs over the five years, highlighting any significant patterns. Comparative analysis will be used to examine year-by-year differences in NPA ratios between SBI and HDFC Bank, and if available, a sector-wise comparison of NPAs will be included. Statistical tests such as t-tests or ANOVA will be applied to determine the significance of differences in NPAs between the banks over the specified period. The results will be interpreted to understand the factors influencing NPA trends and their implications for bank performance and risk management.

The final phase, report writing, will span 4 weeks. The report will be structured into sections, including an introduction that provides background on SBI and HDFC Bank and the importance of NPAs, a literature review summarizing existing studies on NPAs, and the methodology detailing data collection and analysis methods. The results section will present the findings from descriptive, trend, comparative, and statistical analyses. The discussion will interpret these results, compare them with existing literature, and discuss implications for bank performance and risk management. The report will conclude with a

summary of findings and recommendations for future research or policy changes. References to all sources, including annual reports and relevant literature, will be provided. This structured approach ensures a comprehensive and systematic comparative study of NPAs in SBI and HDFC Bank.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Data analysis is the process of analyzing, cleansing, manipulating and modeling data in order to identify usable information, inform conclusions and help in decision making. The goal of analysis is to take current data from a single or several sources and utilize it to make the best conclusion possible. Data interpretation refers to the application of procedures that examine data in order to get an informed conclusion. Data interpretation gives meaning of the information that has been evaluated and determines its significance. In order to find impact of NPA on profitability, total advances, gross NPA, net NPA and the trends of NPA the following analyses have been undertaken.

REASON FOR ASSETS BECOMING NON-PERFORMING ASSETS

A loan is in arrears when principal or interest payments are late or missed. A loan is in default when the lender considers the loan agreement to be broken and debtor is unable to meet its obligations, non-performing loans tend to occur during economic hardships when delinquencies are high. They happen when the borrower fails to make payment for a long period of time.

IMPACT OF NPA ON PROFITABILITY

The impact of Non-Performing Assets (NPAs) on profitability refers to how the presence of NPAs within a financial institution or a company can affect its overall financial performance and profitability. NPAs are loans or advances that have not been repaid by borrowers as per the agreed terms, typically because of default or delayed payments.

TABLE – 1

IMPACT OF NPA ON PROFITABILITY OF SBI BANK – CORRELATION ANALYSIS

HYPOTHESIS:

The following is the hypothesis is tested in this resaerch

Ho: There is no relationship between NPA and profitability of selected banks.

Ha: There is a relationship between NPA and profitability of selected banks.

PARTICULARS	GPM	NPM	OPM	ROA	ROE
GNPA	0.271	0.994	0.257	0.999	0.987
NNPA	0.391	0.975	0.377	0.968	0.963
PCR	-0.268	0.967	-0.275	0.943	0.967

The Table – 1 consists impact of NPA on profitability of SBI bank of five years GNPA has a Gross Profit Margin (GPM) of 0.271 and a Net Profit Margin (NPM) of 0.994. A high GPM indicates that the company is generating a good profit relative to its total revenue. A high NPM suggests that the company is efficient in controlling its expenses and generating a significant net profit. In this case, high GNPA does not seem to have a significant negative impact on profitability, as both GPM and

NPM are high.

NNPA has a GPM of 0.391 and an NPM of 0.975. Both GPM and NPM are relatively high, indicating that the company is profitable. Similar to GNPA, high NNPA does not appear to have a substantial negative impact on profitability, as both GPM and NPM are high. PCR has a negative GPM (-0.268) and a high NPM (0.967). A negative GPM suggests that the company is not generating sufficient profit to cover its provisioning for bad loans, which can be a concern. A negative GPM combined with a high NPM indicates that while the company is generating a good net profit, it may not be adequately provisioning for its bad loans. This could be a potential risk to the company's financial health in the long term.

The impact of NPA on profitability appears to vary depending on the specific metric. High levels of GNPA and NNPA do not seem to significantly impact profitability, as both GPM and NPM are high. However, the negative GPM for PCR suggests that the provisioning for bad loans may be a concern for the company's financial performance despite a high NPM. Further analysis and context about the company's financial situation and industry norms would be needed to make a more comprehensive assessment of the impact of NPA on profitability during the period of the study.

From the above correlation analysis null hypothesis is accepted and alternative hypothesis is rejected for SBI bank.

TABLE – 2

IMPACT OF NPA ON PROFITABILITY OF HDFC BANK – CORRELATION ANALYSIS

HYPOTHESIS:

The following hypothesis is tested in this research

Ho: There is no relationship between NPA and profitability of selected banks.

Ha: There is a relationship between NPA and profitability of selected banks.

PARTICULARS	GPM	NPM	OPM	ROA	ROE
GNPA	-0.128	-0.778	-0.775	-0.631	-0.806
NNPA	-0.222	-0.637	-0.786	-0.486	-0.667
PCR	0.197	-0.684	-0.487	-0.859	-0.817

Chart - 2
IMPACT OF NPA ON PROFITABILITY OF HDFC BANK
- CORRELATION ANALYSIS

The Table – 2 consists of impact on profitability of HDFC bank of five years GNPA and NNPA both have a negative impact on NPM. The presence of NPAs affects the bank's net income negatively, as provisions are made to cover potential losses from bad loans. As a result, the net profit decreases, leading to a lower NPM, Similar to NPM, both GNPA and NNPA negatively impact OPM. As the bank sets aside provisions to cover bad loans, it reduces the operating profit. Hence, the OPM decreases. GNPA and NNPA both have a negative impact on ROA. ROA measures how efficiently a bank uses its assets to generate profit. When a significant portion of assets turns into NPAs, it hampers the bank's ability to generate income from those assets. Consequently, ROA decreases. GNPA and NNPA also negatively affect ROE. ROE measures the bank's profitability in relation to its shareholders' equity. When NPAs increase, the bank's net profit decreases, which leads to a lower ROE as the return to equity holders diminishes.

The gross and net NPAs, have a negative impact on the profitability of HDFC Bank. They can reduce profit margins, decrease return metrics, and necessitate provisions that further reduce profitability. Managing and reducing NPAs is crucial for banks to maintain and improve their profitability.

From the above correlation analysis null hypothesis is rejected and alternative hypothesis is accepted for HDFC bank.

FINDINGS, SUGGESTION AND CONCLUSION

It is concluded that the project by giving the findings and conclusion of non- performing assets.

FINDINGS

- ✓ **SBI:** High levels of GNPA and NNPA do not significantly impact profitability metrics (GPM, NPM). However, the negative Gross Profit Margin (GPM) in relation to Provision Coverage Ratio (PCR) indicates potential concerns about adequate provisioning for bad loans.
- ✓ **HDFC Bank:** High GNPA and NNPA significantly reduce profitability metrics (GPM, NPM, OPM, ROA, ROE), highlighting the substantial negative impact of NPAs on financial performance. The PCR also contributes to decreased profitability, reflecting strain on the bank's returns.

SUGGESTION

SBI should enhance provisioning strategies to address potential long-term risks, while HDFC Bank should prioritize reducing NPAs to improve profitability and financial stability.

CONCLUSION

The analysis reveals that while SBI maintains strong profitability despite high NPAs, it faces potential concerns about adequate provisioning. In contrast, HDFC Bank experiences a significant negative impact on profitability due to high NPAs, with both GNPA and NNPA adversely affecting key financial metrics. Effective NPA management is crucial for both banks, but the challenges and outcomes vary.

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